

THE ROLE OF YOUTH IN ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION WITH REFERENCE TO BIO DEGRADABLE AND DISPOSABLE PRODUCTS

Krishna Dhamodaran*, Dr. D. Divya Prabha**, S. Selva Krishna*** & Dr. V. B. Mathipurani***

* Student, PSG Institute of Advanced Studies, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu

** Associate Professor, PSG Institute of Advanced Studies, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu

*** Assistant Professor, PSG Institute of Advanced Studies, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu

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Abstract:

Youth are an important constituency in the conservation of biodiversity and have a huge impact on it. They are energetic, technology-savvy, constantly evolving, oriented to problem-solving and often propagate active consumerism. Their strong comprehension on sustainability which advocates for reduction in footprints and improved quality of life across sectors and industries is essential for the future. The crucial role of biodiversity in the ecological services provisioning, regulating cultural and supporting and its relevancy to sustainability has to be well understood and linked to daily life. Hence youth should be informed and educated on the dependency of biodiversity for survival. While younger youth are potential voters in affecting future policies; older ones hold decision-making status in the government and industry to actually shape strategic directions. The conclusion is that the youths are been satisfied with the service and quality of the product but further enhancements and improvements has to be done to increase the sales volume an profit in future period of time.

Key Words: Biodiversity, Service and Quality & Sales Volume

Introduction:

Young people are one of the most promising sectors of the society. They can be promoters of change, young as they are because of their natural dynamism and will power, they can bring fresh perspective, energy, drive and a sense of what is possible. Youth in the academe, being educated and informed have greater opportunity to be involved and take part in addressing environmental concerns. There's much we can do to learn and support their efforts. Young people constitute a large part of the world's population. Demographic statistics reveal that children under 15 comprise nearly one-third of the world's total population with 60 percent of them living in Asia. Undoubtedly, the youth can significantly perform vital roles in the society. It is imperative that youth from all parts of the world participate actively in all relevant levels of decision making processes because it affects their lives today and has implications for their futures.

Statement of the Problem:

Youth preference plays a major role in all parts of the services rendered by the company. This study is used to predict the over-all youth preference towards the Bio degradable disposable products manufactured and sold by the company.

Objectives of the Study:

- To assess youth preference towards the various products related to bio degradable and disposable products. .
- To know about the level of satisfaction of youths towards various products used by them.
- To know about the level of acceptance of the youths towards preferring the products of various companies.
- To know about the durability of using the product by the youths.
- To analyze the youths attitude towards purchasing the product from the companies manufacturing bio degradable and disposable products.

Scope of the Study: The scope of the study is to investigate the different youth's preference and satisfaction level towards Bio degradable disposable products manufactured and sold by the company. The study is undertaken on the basis of sample survey of the respondents in Coimbatore area.

Research Methodology:

Types of Research: Descriptive research is used for collecting the data.

Data Collection Procedure Used in my Research: Questionnaire

Field Work: The data was collected from the customer base of the company in and around Coimbatore.

Data Collection Techniques:

- **Primary Data:** Questionnaire
- **Secondary Data:** Internet, Websites and Journals

Data Interpretation Tools: Following software's has been used during analysis and compiling of data. Percentage analysis, Multiple regression and Anova.

Limitations of the Study:

- The study is limited to only one company.
- The sample size is limited to 150 and that may be a bias of the study.
- The study period is around 3 months and a deep analysis about the research cannot be made.
- Respondent may fail to express their opinions and beliefs.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Demo-Graphic Variables	Particulars	Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	97	64.7
	Female	53	35.3
	Total	150	100
Age	18 -25 years	8	5.3
	26 -35 years	8	5.3
	36 – 45 years	75	50
	45 years & above	59	39.3
	Total	150	100
Educational qualification	School level education	16	10.7
	Graduate	67	44.7
	Post graduate	37	24.7
	Professional	30	20
	Total	150	100
Occupational status	Student	15	10
	House wife	29	19.3
	Working women	30	20
	Professionals	53	35.3
	Employed	8	5.3
	Business	15	10
	Total	150	100
Monthly income	5000-10000/month	19	14.6
	Below 5,000	16	10.7
	5,000 – 10,000	74	49.3
	10,000 – 20,000	38	25.3
	Above 20,000	22	14.7
	Total	150	100

The above table shows about the gender of the respondents were out of 150 respondents 64.7% are male and 35.3% are female. 5.3% are from the age group of 18-25 years, 5.3% are from the age group of 26-35 years, 50% are from the age group of 36-45 years, 39.3% are from the age group of 45 years and above. 10.7% have completed their school level, 44.7% are graduates, 24.7% are post graduates and 20% are professionals. 10% are students, 19.3% are house wife, 20% are working women, 35.3% are professionals, 5.3% are employed persons, and 10% are business people. 10.7% are earning below 5,000, 49.3% are earning from 5,000-10,000, 25.3% are earning form 10,000-20,000 and 14.7% are earning above 20,000.

Awareness about Biodegradable Disposal Product by Youth:

	Frequency	Percent
Yes	80	53.3
No	70	46.7
Total	150	100

The above table shows about awareness about biodegradable disposal product by youth were out of 150 respondents 53.3% are having awareness about biodegradable products and 46.7% are not having awareness about biodegradable disposal product.

Purchasing Bio-Degradable Disposal Product by Youth:

	Frequency	Percent
Yes	88	58.7
No	62	41.3
Total	150	100

The above table shows about purchasing bio-degradable disposal product were out of 150 respondents 58.7% are purchasing bio degradable product and 41.3% are not purchasing bio-degradable disposal product by youth.

Level of Acceptance towards Using Good Quality by the Companies:

	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Agree	21	14
Agree	54	36
Neutral	52	34.7
Disagree	7	4.7
Strongly Disagree	16	10.7
Total	150	100

The above table shows about the level of acceptance towards using good quality by the company were out of 150 respondents 14% strongly agree, 36% agree, 34.7% are neutral, 4.7% disagree, and 10.7% strongly disagree for level of acceptance towards using good quality.

Level of Acceptance towards Television as a Great Source of Attracting Youth toward Food Containers:

	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Agree	31	20.7
Agree	14	9.3
Neutral	30	20
Disagree	30	20
Strongly Disagree	45	30
Total	150	100

The above table shows about the level of acceptance towards television as a great source of attracting people toward food containers were out of 150 respondents 20.7% strongly agree, 9.3% agree, 20% are neutral, 20% disagree, and 30% strongly disagree. It shows that most of the respondents strongly disagree for television as a great source of attracting youth toward food containers.

Level of Acceptance towards Environment Friendly of the Product:

	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Agree	15	10
Agree	52	34.7
Neutral	31	20.7
Disagree	30	20
Strongly Disagree	22	14.7
Total	150	100

The above table shows about the level of acceptance towards environment friendly of the product were out of 150 respondents 10% strongly agree, 34.7% agree, 20.7% are neutral, 20% disagree, and 14.7% strongly disagree. It shows that most of the respondents agree for environment friendly of the product.

Level of Satisfaction towards First Use Experience:

	Frequency	Percent
Satisfied	52	34.7
Neutral	59	39.3
Dissatisfied	23	15.3
Highly Dissatisfied	16	10.7
Total	150	100

The above table shows about the level of satisfaction towards purchase experience were out of 150 respondents 4.7% highly satisfied, 34% are satisfied, 35.3% are neutral, 20% are dissatisfied and 15.3% are highly dissatisfied. It shows that most of the respondents are neutral towards purchase experience.

Comparison Between Age and Factors Related to Level of Satisfaction:

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.664	0.227		16.174	0
	Level of satisfaction towards value	-0.44	0.058	-0.474	-7.527	0
	Level of satisfaction towards purchase experience	0.094	0.083	0.134	1.13	0.261
	Level of satisfaction towards first use experience	0.14	0.082	0.173	1.717	0.088
	Level of satisfaction towards	0.036	0.048	0.052	0.755	0.452

packaging					
Level of satisfaction towards after purchase service	-0.272	0.071	-0.297	-3.832	0
Level of satisfaction towards having products in stock	0.809	0.07	0.983	11.471	0
Level of satisfaction towards Special offers, discounts and rewards	0.128	0.052	0.201	2.454	0.015
Level of satisfaction towards the range of pack / portion sizes	-0.064	0.068	-0.092	-0.938	0.35
Level of satisfaction towards usage experience	-0.127	0.051	-0.172	-2.492	0.014
Level of satisfaction towards after purchase service	-0.493	0.054	-0.592	-9.096	0
Level of satisfaction towards packaging	-0.028	0.045	-0.035	-0.614	0.54
Level of satisfaction towards commitment to the environment	0.048	0.033	0.088	1.47	0.144
a. Dependent Variable: Age group					

Model Fit:

Age (Dependent variable) (Constant) 1.309= Level of satisfaction towards value (-0.440) + Level of satisfaction towards purchase experience (0.094) + Level of satisfaction towards first use experience (0.140)+ Level of satisfaction towards packaging (0.036) + Level of satisfaction towards after purchase service (-0.272)+ Level of satisfaction towards having products in stock (0.809) + Level of satisfaction towards Special offers, discounts and rewards (0.128)+ Level of satisfaction towards the range of pack / portion sizes (-0.064) + Level of satisfaction towards usage experience (-0.127)+ Level of satisfaction towards after purchase service (-0.493)+ Level of satisfaction towards packaging (-0.028) + Level of satisfaction towards commitment to the environment (0.048).

It shows that the factors Level of satisfaction towards purchase experience, Level of satisfaction towards first use experience, Level of satisfaction towards having products in stock, Level of satisfaction towards Special offers, discounts and rewards Level of satisfaction towards commitment to the environment are directly proportional to age.

The factors level of satisfaction towards value, level of satisfaction towards after purchase service, level of satisfaction towards the range of pack / portion sizes, level of satisfaction towards usage experience, level of satisfaction towards after purchase service, and level of satisfaction towards packaging are indirectly proportional to age.

One Way Anova:

Comparison between Educational Qualification and Reason for Making Purchase:

H₀: There is no significant relationship between educational qualification and Reason for making purchase

H₁: There is a significant relationship between educational qualification and Reason for making purchase

Descriptive								
Reason for making purchase								
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
School level education	16	2.5	0.516	0.129	2.22	2.78	2	3
Graduate	67	2.34	1.067	0.13	2.08	2.6	1	4
Post graduate	37	2.32	1.226	0.202	1.92	2.73	1	4
Professional	30	2.8	1.095	0.2	2.39	3.21	1	4
Total	150	2.45	1.078	0.088	2.27	2.62	1	4

Interpretation : The above table shows about the mean value of factors related to educational qualification and reason for making purchase were the mean value is high with professionals at 2.80 and they should be concentrated much for the decision making process of the study.

Findings:

- Maximum of the respondents are male in our study.
- Most of the respondents are from the age group of 36-45 years.

- Maximum of the respondents are graduates in our survey.
- Most of the respondents are professionals in our survey.
- Maximum of the respondents are earning from 5,000-10,000.
- Most of the respondents are having awareness about biodegradable disposal product.
- Maximum of the respondents are purchasing bio-degradable disposal product.
- Most of the respondents agree for using good quality by the company.
- Maximum of the respondents strongly disagree for television as a great source of attracting people toward food container.
- Maximum of the respondents are neutral for communicating youth about the product through internet.

Suggestions:

- More advertisements can be given for the need of providing knowledge about the product to the customers so that the sales volume can be increased in future period of time.
- More distributors can be created for increasing the distribution channel so that the brand name can be reached easily among the youths.
- The factors Level of satisfaction towards purchase experience, Level of satisfaction towards first use experience, Level of satisfaction towards having products in stock, Level of satisfaction towards Special offers, discounts and rewards Level of satisfaction towards commitment to the environment are directly proportional to age and these factors can be taken for decision making process of the study.

Conclusion:

The youths are been satisfied with the service and quality of the product but further enhancements and improvements has to be done to increase the sales volume an profit in future period of time.

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